

THE EFFECT OF ALUMINUM ADDITIONS ON INTERFACIAL MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF C/MG-COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of aluminum additions on the interfacial microstructure and the mechanical in- and off-axis properties of different unidirectionally reinforced carbon/magnesium-aluminum-composites were investigated by transmission electron microscopy, thermal analysis, three-point bending, and interlaminar shear testing. Aluminum segregates to the fiber/matrix interface and forms plate- and needle-shaped precipitates. This causes a significant improvement in the off-axis strength at the expense of the in-axis strength. The ratio of the in- to off-axis properties can be optimized by varying the aluminum content.

INTRODUCTION

Excellent stiffness and strength, low weight and comparatively low cost make carbon fibers one of the most favourable reinforcement materials for composites. While carbon fiber reinforced polymers have been used in structural applications for many years, there is now renewed interest in developing carbon fiber reinforced light metals such as aluminum and magnesium. The advantages of the metal matrix composites are the excellent specific mechanical properties even at elevated temperatures [1,2], recyclability [3], good thermal conductivity [4], and moisture resistance [5].

The difficulties associated with the production of C/Mg- and C/Al-composites are of quite different nature. The C/Al-system is thermodynamically rather reactive. The reaction product Al_4C_3 causes an embrittlement of the composites [6]. In contrast, the pure C/Mg-system is thermodynamically relatively stable. The difficulty with this system is the poor wettability between carbon fibers and magnesium that results in improper fiber/matrix interface strength [7]. The aim of the present study is to investigate whether adding aluminum to the magnesium matrix can improve the wetting behavior and the mechanical off-axis properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two types of carbon fibers produced by Toray were used in this study, i.e. high tensile T300J and high modulus M40J. The fibers were incorporated into commercially pure magnesium and into two commercial magnesium-aluminum alloys (AM20 and AZ91) with 2 and 9 wt.% aluminum content. The fiber properties and the nominal composition of the matrix alloys are shown in Table 1 and 2.

Table 1. Properties of the carbon fibers used [8].

	T300J	M40J
Tensile strength (MPa)	4210	4410
Tensile modulus (GPa)	230	377
Density (g/cm ³)	1.79	1.77

Table 2. Nominal composition of the matrix alloys in wt.% [9].

	Al	Zn	Mn	Mg
AM20 HP	1.7-2.2	0.1 (max)	0.5	balance
AZ91 HP	8.0-8.5	0.3-1.0	0.17	balance

Unidirectionally reinforced metal matrix composites with approximately 63 vol.% fiber content were produced with a gas pressure melt infiltration process that has been described in previous papers [10,11].

The in- and off-axis properties of the different composites in the as-cast condition were investigated by three-point bending tests at room temperature. For the determination of the bending strength flat laminate specimens were used with the dimensions of 1x10x45 mm³. This corresponds to a span length to specimen thickness ratio of 40. The interlaminar shear strength (ILS) was measured by the short beam method. For all composite systems, a span length to thickness ratio of 5 was chosen. The dimensions of the ILS-samples were 4x10x25 mm³. All bending tests were performed with a 100 kN Instron machine at a crosshead speed of 1 mm/min.

Differential thermal analysis of the unreinforced matrix systems and of the composite systems in the as-cast conditions were carried out in an argon atmosphere at a heating rate of 5 K/min with a Netsch STA 409 analysis apparatus.

The specimens for transmission electron microscopy were prepared by the standard cross section technique under use of oil as a lubricant to prevent the serious corrosion problems arising from the thin specimens acting as a multielectrode galvanic cell in contact with water. Slices were cut with the interfaces of interest in perpendicular orientation to the surface, followed by grinding, dimpling and final ion thinning to electron transparency [12,13]. For the HVEM investigations, we used a JEOL-JEM 1000 high-voltage electron microscope operated at 1000 kV. A Philips CM-20-twin electron microscope equipped with a Tracor-EDX spectrometer was used for investigating the interface phenomena down to the atomic scale as well as to characterize the microchemistry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MECHANICAL TESTING

Fig. 1 presents the results of bending and interlaminar shear tests. The aluminum content of the matrix influences the in- and off-axis properties of all composites [11].

Figure 1. Bending and interlaminar shear strength of C/Mg-composites.

Generally, aluminum improves the off-axis strength of the C/Mg-Al-composites but reduces the in-axis strength. This influence is particularly noticeable in the case of the T300J/Mg-Al-systems and is less pronounced in the case of the M40J reinforcement. In the T300J/AM20-system, the addition of two percent aluminum nearly doubles the ILS while only slightly decreasing the bending strength. However, the addition of nine percent aluminum dramatically reduces the in-axis strength. This significant loss in bending strength did not occur in the M40J/Mg-Al-systems. The bending strength remains on a high level even with a high aluminum content of the matrix. The ILS increases continuously with increasing aluminum content.

DIFFERENTIAL THERMAL ANALYSIS

The difference in mechanical behaviour between the C/Mg-Al-composites cannot be explained by the different mechanical properties of the matrix itself. First, the volume fraction of the matrix is low. Second, one of the matrices (AZ91) had drastically different properties when reinforced with different fiber types. The key aspects must be the properties of the fibers after the infiltration process and the reactions at the fiber/matrix interface. Information about these reactions can be obtained from differential thermal analysis. The melting range of the C/Mg-Al-composites is significantly higher in temperature than the melting range of the unreinforced matrix (Fig. 2 and 3). This effect cannot be explained by physical processes such as preferential melting at fiber interfaces or differences in the thermal conductivity of the DTA-samples between the unreinforced matrix and the composites. The aluminum free T300J/Mg- and M40J/Mg-systems do not show a dependence on fiber type and no shift of the DTA-peaks towards higher temperatures compared to the pure

unreinforced magnesium. The DTA-measurements (Fig. 2 and 3) clearly indicate a reduction in the amount of aluminum in solid solution in the matrix when fibers are introduced. This reduction is influenced by the fiber type. T300J/AZ91 and T300J/AM20 have almost no aluminum left in solid solution in the matrix because of the strong reaction with the fibers. In the case of the M40J reinforcement, this effect is much less pronounced.

Figure 2. DTA-curves for reinforced and unreinforced AM20.

Figure 3. DTA-curves for reinforced and unreinforced AZ91.

INTERFACE MICROSTRUCTURE

The aim of the presented TEM investigations is to relate the interface microstructure of differently composed metal-matrix composites to their mechanical properties as discussed above.

Figure 4. Plate- and needle-shaped precipitates at the fiber/matrix interface of a T300J/AZ91 composite (middle part: matrix).

A relatively high content of 9 wt.% of aluminum in the matrix alloy (AZ91) causes a large reaction zone near the interface to the reinforcing T300J fibers. As can be seen in Fig. 4 two kinds of plate- and needle-shaped precipitates have formed. Employing EDX microanalysis (cf. Fig. 5) and electron diffraction, most of the plates extending into the matrix with a length of up to 1 μm were identified as the intermetallic $\text{Mg}_{17}\text{Al}_{12}$. The amount of oxygen being present in the EDX-spectrum of this phase (cf. Fig. 5 - 2) possibly results from the atmospheric influence during specimen preparation. The smaller needle-shaped precipitates near the fiber surface in Fig. 4 having a length of only 100 nm very likely consist of Al_4C_3 which should result from the reaction of the matrix aluminum with the carbon fibers under the processing conditions used.

As Fig. 6 demonstrates, a decrease in the aluminum content of the matrix to 2 wt.% (AM20) consequently leads to much less precipitates being present in the interface. Taking into consideration that the observed precipitates should substantially increase the bonding in the interface they should also increase the interlaminar shear strength, i.e. the off-axis properties of the composite. This corresponds well to the mechanical measurements shown in Fig. 1.

In composites with T300J fibers thin graphitic interlayers were found which should be formed by pyrolysis of the fiber sizing polymer in the gas pressure melt infiltration process during heating of the fiber preform in an inert gas atmosphere at several hundred degrees C. An example of such a 10 nm thick layer is shown in the HREM-image in Fig. 7 with the graphite lattice planes parallelly oriented to the fiber surface. Probably, this graphitic interlayer promotes the heterogeneous nucleation of the precipitates growing from the fiber into the matrix with epitaxial orientation, according to [14], were parallel orientation between the (0003) planes of aluminum carbide and (002) graphite plane was found.

Figure 5. EDX analysis of a T300J/AZ91 composite. The TEM micrograph shows the fiber on the right and the Mg matrix with precipitates on the left.

Figure 6. Precipitates at the fiber/matrix interface in a T300J/AM20 composite (middle part: matrix).

Figure 7. Graphite layer on the fiber surface in a T300J/AM20 composite (fiber below).

Figure 8. Pores at fiber surface and debonding in a M40J/AM20 composite (middle part: matrix).

In case of using the high modulus fibers M40J in a low aluminum alloyed magnesium matrix, however, precipitates are completely absent as can be seen in Fig. 8. Further on, most fibers are debonded from the matrix. Although this may be influenced by the preparation procedure, it clearly demonstrates the weak interface bonding, which is in contrast to the situation shown in Fig. 4. Consequently, the off-axis properties of the M40J containing composites must be poor (cf. Fig. 1). The absence of aluminum rich precipitates in M40J fiber reinforced composites confirms the results of the DTA-analysis of these materials presented in Fig. 2, i.e. their melting temperature resembles that of the unreinforced alloy.

Quantitative EDXS measurements revealed a content of approximately 10 wt.% of magnesium distributed in the volume of the T300J fibers. Contrary, in case of M40J fibers Mg was observed only in a thin (100-200nm) surface near region. This difference in the Mg-infiltration behavior results

from the high-tensile strength T300J fiber offering a more porous structure than the graphitized high-modulus M40J one (cf. [15]).

The magnesium diffusion into the carbon fibers should result in a degradation of their mechanical properties, especially in the case of the T300J fiber. Both the fiber damage caused by the chemical interface reaction discussed above and the fiber degradation by Mg diffusion are assumed to be responsible for the course of the in-axis properties of the composites shown in Fig. 1.

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